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5 REASONS TO ENCOURAGE SHARING RESEARCH SOFTWARE

Reproducibility: It enables to replicate published findings by running the same computational tool on data generated by the study

FAIR Principles: It ensures research tools are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

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